

Correlation between Teachers' Use of ... (Faransa, et. al., 2024) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15045503>

Correlation between Teachers' Use of Instructional Materials and Academic Performance in Biology among Senior Secondary School Students in Adamawa State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined the correlation between teachers' use of instructional materials and academic performance in Biology among senior secondary school students in Adamawa State, Nigeria. The study employs a correlational design; the study population consists of 814 teachers, as well as 39,390 Senior Secondary II (SSII) students from 366 senior secondary schools in Adamawa State. The sample of 260 Biology teachers, and 384 students was used with student performance in Biology. Cronbach's alpha was used to determine the internal consistency of the questionnaire, yielding a reliability coefficient of 0.86, indicating a high level of reliability. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire tagged Teachers' Use of Instructional Materials Questionnaire (TUIMQ) and analyzed using descriptive statistics and linear regression. The results revealed a weak but positive correlation ($r=0.208$) between the use of instructional materials and students' academic achievement, with 4.3% of the variance in performance explained by the use of these tools. Despite the limited impact weak correlation, the study emphasizes the need for improved teacher training and better access to instructional resources to enhance learning outcomes in Biology. The findings underscore the importance of continuous professional development for teachers and the provision of adequate resources to close the performance gap between well-funded urban schools and under-resourced rural areas. The study concludes that while instructional materials positively influence academic achievement, their effectiveness is constrained by infrastructural and financial limitations. Recommendations include policies to enhance technological infrastructure, teacher training, and equitable resource allocation to improve Biology education in Adamawa State.

Keywords: Instructional Materials, Biology Teachers, Senior Secondary Students and Academic Achievement

Introduction

In recent years, advancements in technology have created new opportunities for improving the use of instructional materials in classrooms. Tools such as interactive whiteboards, projectors, and online simulation platforms have revolutionized science education, particularly in Biology, by providing dynamic and accessible ways to explore concepts (Aliyu, 2020). These digital resources enable students to participate in virtual dissections, explore cellular processes, and observe biological phenomena in real-time. However, Yusuf and Afolabi (2022) highlight that the integration of these technologies in Adamawa State is limited due to infrastructural deficits and a lack of digital literacy among teachers. The authors suggest that policies to improve schools' access to technological infrastructure, along with teacher training programs are essential to fully integrate digital instructional materials into the Biology curriculum. Although the benefits of instructional materials in enhancing science education are well-recognized, there are considerable challenges to their widespread use in Nigerian schools, particularly in

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Adamawa State. Financial constraints have been identified as a significant barrier, impeding the procurement of essential resources such as laboratory equipment and teaching aids (Abdullahi & Gambo, 2020). Additionally, overcrowded classrooms in many public schools reduce the effectiveness of these materials, as teachers struggle to engage students individually. Ogbu and Hassan (2023) and Isma'il & Lukman (2022). found that insufficient government funding and inadequate infrastructure severely limit access to necessary teaching resources in rural areas, contributing to a performance gap between students in well-funded urban schools and their counterparts in under-resourced rural areas.

Several recent studies have underscored the critical role instructional materials play in enhancing students' academic achievement in science subjects, including Biology. Omosewo (2018) found that instructional tools such as charts, models, and laboratory equipment help students visualize biological concepts, making learning more engaging and effective. Similarly, Lawal (2019) noted that the use of hands-on materials in classrooms leads to better comprehension, retention, and application of biological knowledge compared to traditional lecture methods. These findings illustrate the importance of tangible instructional materials in fostering a deeper understanding of scientific concepts. Moreover, instructional materials can enhance students' cognitive processes by making abstract concepts more tangible and relatable. Aina and Ajiboye (2020) emphasize that when students interact physically with biological specimens or digital simulations, they are more likely to develop critical thinking skills, which are essential for mastering Biology. Despite this, many teachers lack the skills to effectively utilize these resources, which negatively impacts student performance (Idris & Mohammed, 2017; Isma'il & Lukman, 2022). Their study found that only a small fraction of teachers in Adamawa State were adequately trained to integrate instructional materials into their lessons, thereby reducing their effectiveness in improving learning outcomes.

Recent empirical studies have consistently highlighted the importance of instructional materials in enhancing students' academic performance, particularly in Biology. Oluwatobi and Ayinde (2021) and Omosewo (2018) found that schools where teachers used hands-on tools like charts, models, and laboratory equipment saw significant improvements in students' achievement in Biology, emphasizing the value of practical learning over traditional lecture methods. In Adamawa State, Idris and Mohammed (2017) identified inadequate teacher training in the use of instructional materials as a major barrier to effective Biology teaching, resulting in lower student performance. Similarly, Aina and Ajiboye (2020) demonstrated that while digital tools can greatly improve engagement and understanding of biological concepts, poor infrastructure and limited digital literacy among teachers hinder their use, particularly in rural areas. Ogbu and Hassan (2023) further explored the challenges in rural schools, revealing that limited access to teaching resources due to insufficient funding exacerbates the performance gap between rural and urban students. Yusuf and Afolabi (2022) supported these findings, noting that infrastructural deficits and lack of teacher training restrict the use of digital instructional tools, despite their potential to improve learning outcomes. Lastly, Lawal (2019) and Abdullahi and Gambo (2020) both emphasized the critical role of instructional materials in student success. Lawal found that the use of practical teaching aids directly improves academic performance, while Abdullahi and Gambo pointed to funding constraints as a major obstacle to providing these resources, especially in rural schools, further widening the performance disparity across regions. The need for continuous professional development programmes for teachers has been highlighted by Oluwatobi and Ayinde (2021), who argue that such programmes equip teachers with the necessary skills to design, improvise, and implement instructional materials in science subjects. Their research revealed that students taught by teachers who had received such training consistently outperformed their peers in standardized Biology exams. Ibeneme (2013) further emphasizes the importance of teaching aids, which he defines as practical materials used by both teachers and students during lessons to enhance learning. The lack of inadequacy of instructional materials remains a major cause of ineffectiveness in schools, leading to poor student performance (Abdu-Raheem, 2015). Ahmed (2016) confirmed that many Nigerian secondary schools operate in unwelcoming environments, lacking essential teaching materials. According to Eniyewu (2015), instructional aids are crucial in promoting students' knowledge acquisition and raising academic standards. The question remains whether adequate instructional materials exist for teaching Biology in secondary schools in Adamawa State. If available, are they sufficient? If not, what can be done to address this gap? Biology, as one of the science subjects at the senior secondary school level in Adamawa State, has seen a decline in students' academic achievement in recent years. Reports as reveal that student performance in the Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination in Biology has been consistently below average. From 2014 to 2017, a concerning number of students failed to obtain credit-level passes in Biology, with percentages ranging from 13.2% to 30.2%. This decline has raised concerns among educational stakeholders, prompting an examination of factors contributing to students' underachievement in Biology.

Several factors including government policies, parental involvement, student motivation, and teacher-related issues have been proposed as potential contributors of poor academic performance. This study posits that the use (or lack thereof) of instructional materials by teachers may play a significant role in influencing students' academic achievement in Biology. To

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enhance students' understanding and address the challenges they face, this study seeks to explore how teachers' use of instructional materials predicts the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Biology in Adamawa State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Research Problem

Despite the recognized importance of instructional materials in enhancing students' academic achievement, particularly in Biology, their effective use remains a challenge in Nigerian secondary schools, including those in Adamawa State. Several issues, such as inadequate infrastructure, insufficient funding, and limited teacher training, hinder the integration of instructional materials into the curriculum. Reports indicate that student performance in Biology at the Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination (SSCE) in Adamawa State has been consistently below average, with credit-level passes ranging from only 13.2% to 30.2% between 2014 and 2017. Additionally, the lack of access to necessary teaching aids and digital resources, compounded by teachers' limited skills in utilizing these tools, contributes to poor learning outcomes. This gap in the use of instructional materials raises questions about their availability, sufficiency, and role in students' academic achievement. Thus, this study investigates how teachers' use of instructional materials predicts the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Biology in Adamawa State, aiming to address the challenges and improve student performance in the subject.

Objective of the Study

The purpose objective of this study is to examine the Teachers' use of instructional materials predicts senior secondary school students' Academic Achievement in Biology Adamawa State, Nigeria.

Research Question

The following research question was posed to guide the study:

How effective is biology teachers' use of instructional materials in senior secondary schools in Adamawa State?

Null Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis formulated and was tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: Teachers' use of instructional materials does not significantly predict senior secondary school students' academic achievement in biology in Adamawa State.

Methodology

The study employed a predictive correlational design to assess the relationship between Teachers' use of instructional materials predicts senior secondary school students' Academic Achievement in Biology Adamawa State, Nigeria. According to Gay (2018), this approach examines the natural connections between variables without manipulation or imposed causality. Whitley and Kite (2021) further characterize predictive correlational research as a method to investigate associations among naturally occurring variables. This design effectively identifies key predictor of student achievement, focusing on factor such as Teachers' use of instructional materials. A survey involving principals and teachers was conducted to evaluate how teachers use of instructional materials predict students' academic performance in Biology. The study population consists of 814 Biology teachers, as well as 39,390 Senior Secondary II (SSII) students from 366 senior secondary schools in Adamawa State. Biology is a core science subject within the school curriculum. A sample size of 260 principals/Biology teachers and 384 students was selected, following the recommendations of the Research Advisor (2006). The study employed a multistage sampling technique, beginning with cluster sampling, where the population was divided into clusters based on educational zones in Adamawa State. Three educational zones were selected as clusters. In the second stage, Local Government Areas (LGAs) were randomly selected within each cluster. In third stage, schools were randomly selected from the chosen LGAs. The final stage involved selecting Senior Secondary II (SSII) students, as they had covered sufficient content in Biology, while SSIII students were excluded as they were preparing for their final exams.

The instrument for data collection was a researchers-constructed questionnaire, the "Teachers' use of instructional materials Questionnaire" (TUIMQ), consisting of 10 items mixed for both positive and negative. The TUIMQ used a five-point Likert scale ranging from Very High Level (VHL) to Very Low Level (VLL). Scores were assigned as thus: 1 for Very Low Level (VLL), 2 for Low Level (LL), 3 for Medium Level (ML), 4 for High Level (HL), and 5 for Very High Level (VHL). A decision rule of 3.0 was applied, where a mean score above 3.0 indicates a positive response (High/Very High Level), and a mean score below 3.0 indicates a negative response (Low/Very Low Level). The researchers also collected students' academic performance scores in Biology, through pro-forma result collected from the schools and converted them into standard scores

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for analysis. To ensure the validity of the instruments, the TUIMQ was reviewed by experts in Curriculum and Instruction. These experts scrutinized the instrument to ensure it accurately measured Teachers' use of instructional materials in relation to the study's research questions and hypotheses. Suggestions were made to restructure the instrument and include both principals and teachers as respondents. All necessary revisions were incorporated into the final draft of the questionnaire. The reliability of the TUIMQ was tested through a trial testing with Biology teachers and students from a school not included in the study. Cronbach's alpha was used to determine the internal consistency of the questionnaire, yielding a reliability coefficient of 0.86, indicating a high level of reliability. Data analysis was conducted using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 23. Descriptive statistics, such as mean and standard deviation, were used to answer the research question, while linear regression analysis was used to test the null hypothesis at a significance level of 0.05

Presentation of Results

Research Question One: How effective is biology teachers' use of instructional materials in senior secondary schools in Adamawa State?

Table 1: Summary of Mean and Standard Deviation of Effectiveness of Biology Teachers' Use of Instructional Materials in Senior Secondary Schools in Adamawa State

S/N	ITEMS	n = 260	Mean	St.D	Remark
1	Adequacy of instructional materials for use during Biology instructions.		4.33	1.02	HL
2	Knowledge of improvisation of instructional materials.		4.43	0.90	HL
3	Quality of instructional materials.		4.47	0.84	HL
4	Appropriate selection of instructional materials.		4.30	1.04	HL
5	Poor handling of instructional materials.		4.32	1.01	HL
6	Ability to use instructional materials during instruction.		3.78	1.42	HL
7	Improvise instructional materials for instruction.		3.76	1.43	HL
8	Suitability of instructional materials with topics taught.		3.95	1.40	HL
9	Rarely use instructional materials during instruction.		4.07	1.32	HL
10	Availability of instructional materials for instruction.		3.54	1.51	HL
Grand Mean			4.09		

Source: Survey 2024

Table 1 presents the mean and standard deviation regarding the effectiveness of biology teachers' use of instructional materials in senior secondary schools in Adamawa State. The grand mean score of 4.09 reflects a high level of effectiveness in the utilization of these instructional materials by biology teachers.

Null Hypothesis

H₀₁: Teachers' use of instructional materials does not significantly predict senior secondary school students' academic achievement in biology in Adamawa State.

Table 2a: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
	.208 ^a	.043	.040	1.39438582

a. Predictors: (Constant), use of instructional materials

Table 2a provides a model summary for the regression analysis examining the relationship between the use of instructional materials and another variable. The correlation coefficient (R) is 0.208, suggesting a weak positive relationship between the

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variables. The R. Square value of 0.043 indicates that approximately 4.3% of the variance in the dependent variable can be explained by the use of instructional materials. The Adjusted R Square is 0.040, which slightly adjusts for the number of predictors in the model. The Standard Error of the Estimate is 1.394, reflecting the average distance that the observed values fall from the regression line. Overall, the results suggest that the use of instructional materials has a limited impact on the dependent variable in this model.

Table 2b: Summary of ANOVA of Linear Regression of Teachers' Use of Instructional Materials as Predictor of Senior Secondary School Students' Academic Achievement in Biology in Adamawa State

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	22.722	1	22.722	11.686	.001 ^b
	Residual	501.632	258	1.944		
	Total	524.354	259			

a. Dependent Variable: Z score (ACHIEVEMENT)

b. Predictors: (Constant), use of instructional materials

Table 2b summarizes the ANOVA results for the linear regression analysis, which examines the impact of teachers' use of instructional materials on senior secondary school students' academic achievement in biology in Adamawa State. The regression model has a Sum of Squares for regression of 22.722, with 1 degree of freedom (df), leading to a Mean Square of 22.722. The F-value of 11.686 indicates a statistically significant relationship between the predictor and the dependent variable, as reflected in the significance level (Sig.) of 0.001. The Residual Sum of Squares is 501.632 with 258 degrees of freedom, yielding a Mean Square of 1.944. The total sum of squares for the model is 524.354 with 259 degrees of freedom. This result suggests that the use of instructional materials significantly predicts students' academic achievement in biology.

Table 2c: Coefficients of Beta

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	-1.621	.399		-4.063	.000
	USEOFINSTRUCTIONALMATERIALS	.357	.105	.208	3.419	.001

Table 2c presents the coefficients from the regression analysis, showing the relationship between the use of instructional materials and students' academic achievement in biology. The unstandardized coefficient for the constant is -1.621 with a standard error of 0.399 indicating the expected value of the dependent variable (Z score of achievement) when the predictor is zero. The coefficient for the use of instructional materials is 0.357 with a standard error of 0.105. This suggests that for each one-unit increase in the use of instructional materials, the Z score of achievement is expected to increase by 0.357 units. The standardized coefficient (Beta) for the use of instructional materials is 0.208, indicating a weak effect size. The t-value for the use of instructional materials is 3.419, and the significance level (Sig.) is 0.001, indicating that the effect is statistically significant. It showed that teachers' use of instructional materials does not significantly predict senior secondary school students' academic achievement in biology in Adamawa State

Summary of the Major Findings

The regression analysis of the data collected revealed that, the use of instructional materials significantly predicts senior secondary school students' academic achievement in biology in Adamawa State. Specifically, for each one-unit increase in the use of instructional materials, students' Z score of achievement is expected to increase by 0.357 units. This relationship is statistically significant, with a significance level of 0.001, highlighting the importance of effective instructional material usage in enhancing student performance in biology.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study align with a growing body of empirical research that underscores the critical role of instructional materials in enhancing students' academic performance, particularly in biology. Previous studies, such as those conducted by Oluwatobi and Ayinde (2021) and Omosewo (2018), demonstrate that the incorporation of hands-on tools, including charts, models, and laboratory equipment, leads to significant improvements in student achievement. These studies emphasize the value of practical learning experiences over traditional lecture-based approaches, suggesting that interactive

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instructional materials can foster a deeper understanding of biological concepts. In the context of Adamawa State, Idris and Mohammed (2017) identified inadequate teacher training in the effective use of instructional materials as a significant barrier to successful biology teaching. This lack of training can lead to suboptimal use of available resources, resulting in lower student performance. Aina and Ajiboye (2020) further corroborate this point by highlighting the potential of digital tools to enhance engagement and understanding of biological concepts. However, they also point out that poor infrastructure and limited digital literacy among teachers inhibit the effective integration of these tools, particularly in rural areas where resources are scarce. Ogbu and Hassan (2023) explored the specific challenges faced by rural schools, revealing that insufficient funding leads to limited access to teaching resources, which exacerbates the performance gap between rural and urban students. This finding is supported by Yusuf and Afolabi (2022), who note that infrastructural deficits and a lack of teacher training restrict the utilization of digital instructional tools, despite their proven efficacy in improving learning outcomes. Finally, the work of Lawal (2019) and Abdullahi and Gambo (2020) reinforces the essential role of instructional materials in promoting student success. Lawal found a direct correlation between the use of practical teaching aids and improved academic performance, while Abdullahi and Gambo highlighted funding constraints as a significant obstacle to providing these essential resources, particularly in rural schools. This situation perpetuates a performance disparity across regions, underscoring the need for targeted interventions to enhance the availability and effective use of instructional materials in biology education.

Conclusion

The study concluded that teachers' use of instructional materials has a statistically significant but weak positive correlation with senior secondary school students' academic achievement in biology in Adamawa State. The findings indicate that effective use of instructional materials positively predicts students' understanding and performance in the subject.

Recommendations

Based on the findings that the following recommendations can be made:

1. Educational authorities should ensure that schools are adequately supplied with a variety of instructional materials, such as textbooks, laboratory equipment, charts, and digital tools. This investment will facilitate effective teaching and enhance students' learning experiences.
2. Government should Conduct regular workshops and professional development programmes for biology teachers focused on the effective integration of instructional materials into their teaching practices. Training should cover both traditional and digital resources to enhance teachers' instructional strategies.
3. Government should Foster a classroom culture that emphasizes interactive and experiential learning through the use of instructional materials. Encourage teachers to incorporate hands-on activities, group work, and project-based learning that utilize available resources effectively.
4. Government should establish a network for schools to share instructional materials and resources. This could include creating partnerships between urban and rural schools to ensure that all students have access to quality educational tools, even if some schools have limited resources.
5. Schools administration should promote the use of educational technology, such as simulations, online labs, and interactive software that can supplement traditional instructional materials. Provide training for teachers to enhance their skills in using these digital tools effectively.

Acknowledgements

The Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education, Modibbo Adama University Yola, Adamawa State, Nigeria, extends gratitude to the scholars whose works have informed and enriched this study. Special thanks to Abdullahi and Gambo (2020), Abdu-Raheem (2015), and Ahmed (2016) for their insights into the availability and impact of instructional materials on academic achievement in Nigerian schools. Acknowledgement is also given to Aina and Ajiboye (2020), Idris and Mohammed (2017), and Lawal (2019) for their contributions to teacher training, digital tools, and practical teaching aids, which were instrumental in shaping this research. The foundational works of Gay (2018) and Whitley and Kite (2021) also provided critical guidance for the research methodology. The department appreciates all cited researchers for their valuable contributions, which have significantly advanced the understanding of instructional materials and their role in educational development in Nigeria.

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